

Original Research

Value Relevance of Cash Flow Statements in Syrian Banks: Evidence from the Damascus Securities Exchange

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Abstract

This study investigates whether the cash flow statements of banks provide valuable insights for Syrian investors. Using Ohlson's (1995) theoretical framework, which links stock prices to the book value of equity, earnings, and cash flow elements, the research aims to determine if factors like economic instability and investor behavior affect the value relevance of these accounting metrics. A model based on Ohlson's theory analyzes data from 11 Syrian private banks listed on the Damascus Securities Exchange (DSE) from 2010 to 2022. The analysis includes cash flow statement metrics to assess the usefulness of operating, investing, and financing cash flows. The pooled OLS technique, with heteroscedasticity correction, is employed. Findings show that operating cash flows (coefficient = 0.1131815, p-value = 0.224) do not offer insights beyond earnings, indicating they don't explain stock price variations beyond what earnings do. Moreover, substituting operating cash flows with earnings does not significantly enhance the model's explanatory power ($R^2 = 0.5263$ vs. $R^2 = 0.5193$). Similarly, investing cash flows (coefficient = -0.001404, p-value = 0.634) and financing cash flows (coefficient = 0.6836272, p-value = 0.336) reveal no marginal value relevance. These outcomes may reflect the unique Syrian economic conditions, suggesting that cash flows do not improve earnings' predictive power for investors. Policymakers should consider promoting alternative performance metrics, such as adjusted earnings measures and loan portfolio quality, to better assess financial health in crisis contexts.

Keywords: Cash flow statements, emerging markets, value relevance, Ohlson model, operating cash flows, Syrian banks.

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Introduction

International financial reporting standards require that banks, along with other firms, prepare a statement of cash flows, outlining cash flows from operating, investing, and financing activities (Gao, Li, & O'Hanlon, 2019). This obligation was introduced following the implementation of IAS 7 in 1992, which became effective in 1994. Many nations' local accounting frameworks also include similar requirements (Akbar, Shah, & Stark, 2011). However, skepticism has been raised about the applicability of this cash flow categorization to banks, as it seems better suited to industrial businesses (Gao, Li, & O'Hanlon, 2019; Burke & Wieland, 2017).

In response to these concerns, researchers have explored the value relevance of banks' cash flow statements. For instance, Gao et al. (2019) found that the distinction between operating and non-operating cash flows in banks' cash flow statements lacks informativeness. Similarly, Ryan et al. (2006) reported that banks' operating cash flows include mixed-nature items that are less positively associated with stock returns compared to pure operating items, though they still show a stronger association than investing or financing cash flows. Dimitropoulos et al. (2010) indicated that while cash flows are important for bank valuation, they are not as significant as earnings. In contrast, Burke and Wieland (2017) observed a strong positive association between banks' operating cash flows and share prices. Beyond the banking sector, research has also examined the importance of cash flow data for valuation in other industries, though findings remain mixed regarding the practical relevance of cash flow information (Bepari, Rahman, & Taher Molik, 2013; Cheng, Liu, & Schaefer, 1996; Akbar, Shah, & Stark, 2011; Charitou, Clubb, & Andreou, 2000).

Recent studies have further highlighted the dynamic nature of cash flow relevance, particularly during periods of economic uncertainty. For example, Abou-El-Sood (2023) found that the value relevance of cash flows significantly increased during the Covid-19 pandemic, suggesting that investors relied more on cash flows for valuation purposes during times of crisis. However, the study also revealed that the distinction between operating and non-operating cash flows was not particularly informative. Similarly, Čupić, Todorović, and Benković (2023) demonstrated that accounting earnings are more value-relevant than cash flows in non-financial firms, though regulatory improvements can enhance the value relevance of financial information. These findings underscore the importance of context in assessing the relevance of cash flow information.

Despite this increased scrutiny of cash flow statement effectiveness in banking, a clear understanding of their valuation role in emerging markets remains underexplored. This gap is particularly pronounced in Syria, where the economic and regulatory environment may significantly differ from more stable markets, thereby influencing the relevance of accounting information. Adding to the complexity, the value relevance of cash flows and other accounting measures is not a permanent attribute that can be generalized across countries or periods. Many studies have explored the dynamic nature of the usefulness of accounting information (Black & White, 2003; Hellström, 2006; Kimouche & Charchafa, 2022; El-Diftar & Elkalla, 2019). For example, it has been argued that macroeconomic variables and shifts in investor perceptions can alter the informativeness of accounting data over time (Collins, Maydew, & Weiss, 1997; Lev & Zarowin, 1999; Thinggaard &

Damkier, 2008; Hellström, 2006). Furthermore, some studies have analyzed the usefulness of accounting information during financial crises (Adwan, Alhaj-Ismail, & Girardone, 2020; Davis-Friday, Eng, & Liu, 2006; Bepari, Rahman, & Taher Molik, 2013).

The ongoing discourse surrounding the effectiveness of cash flow statements in the banking sector, combined with evidence of changes in the significance of accounting data over time and across nations, underscores the need for deeper investigation into their relevance. This exploration is especially critical in countries facing instability, such as Syria, which provides a unique context for analyzing the value relevance of cash flow statements.

This study aims to evaluate the value relevance of cash flow statements in the context of Syrian private banks, focusing on their usefulness to investors in an emerging market characterized by economic and regulatory instability. Specifically, it examines whether operating, investing, and financing cash flows provide incremental or relative value relevance compared to earnings, using Ohlson's (1995) framework.

To achieve this objective, the study evaluates the usefulness of accounting information sourced from listed private banks in Syria over the period 2010–2022. Models based on Ohlson's (1995) work are employed, and an OLS regression technique is utilized. The results suggest that operating cash flows are not incrementally or relatively value-relevant compared to earnings, and investing and financing cash flows do not provide additional useful information for Syrian investors.

The study's contributions to the existing literature can be emphasized in three key areas. First, it enriches the body of research investigating the value relevance of banks' cash flow statements by demonstrating their usefulness within the Syrian banking sector. While many researchers have concentrated on the value relevance of cash flow statements in non-financial sectors (e.g., Lev & Zarowin, 1999; Garrod, Giner, & Larran, 2000; Akbar, Shah, & Stark, 2011; Bepari, Rahman, & Taher Molik, 2013; Tahat & Alhadab, 2017; Kwon, 2018; Yensen, Huang, & Chiang, 2019; El-Diftar & Elkalla, 2019; Kimouche & Charchafa, 2022), few have addressed the issue in the financial sector. Second, the study's findings support the well-known doubts about the informativeness of banks' cash flow statements in their current form, as their components did not provide incremental or relative value relevance. Third, the study is conducted in an emerging market (DSE), providing evidence and insight into the value relevance of cash flow statements in such markets and offering the opportunity to generalize the results to similar emerging markets.

This study also contributes to the theoretical discourse on value relevance by extending the examination beyond traditional accounting metrics, such as earnings and book values, to focus on the statement of cash flows in the context of Syrian private banks. By investigating the association between cash flow information and market valuations, the study aligns with Ohlson's (1995) framework and addresses the growing scholarly call to explore diverse accounting metrics. The findings aim to enhance clarity regarding how cash flow statements contribute to the decision-usefulness of financial reporting,

particularly in emerging markets with unique economic and regulatory environments like Syria.

This paper is organized into several sections. The second section provides an overview of the Syrian banking system. The third section provides a theoretical framework, followed by a literature review on relevant topics. The fifth section details the model specifications and explains the dataset used in the analysis. In the sixth and seventh sections, the findings are presented, analyzed, and discussed. The paper culminates with concluding remarks.

Institutional background

For many decades and until 2000, publicly owned banks were the only operating banks in Syria. By issuing a decree No. (28) in 2001, the financial sector was widely opened for private investments. This decree allowed the establishment of private banks, currently operating alongside publicly owned banks. The Syrian banking sector was further reformed by authorizing Islamic banks (decree No. 35 in 2005), Micro-finance banks (decree No 15 in 2007), and investment banks (decree No. 56 in 2010) (Al Mashhour, Asalie, Abd Aziz, & Noor, 2020). There are currently 14 private banks operating under the supervision of the Central Bank of Syria, three of them are Islamic banks. These banks are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Syrian private banks

No	Banks' Name	Started	Number of Branches	No
1	Banque Bemo Saudi Fransi	2004	40	1
2	Syria Gulf Bank	2007	11	2
3	The International Bank for Trade & Finance	2004	29	3
4	Bank of Syria & Overseas	2004	30	4
5	Arab Bank- Syria	2006	14	5
6	Ahli Trust Bank- Syria	2005	18	6
7	Bank Byblos-Syria	2005	11	7
8	Fransabank-Syria	2009	11	8
9	Bank of Jordan-Syria	2008	12	9
10	Bank Al-Sharq	2009	9	10
11	Qatar National Bank-Syria	2009	10	11
Islamic Banks				Islamic Banks
1	Al-Baraka Bank	2007	13	1
2	Syria International Islamic Bank	2007	20	2
3	Cham Bank	2007	12	3

Source: Damascus Stock Exchange website

Syria has witnessed longstanding unrest that began in 2011 and caused huge destruction of infrastructure with vital consequences on the Syrian economy as a whole

(Sahyouni & Wang, 2019). The financial sector has experienced severe damages demonstrated in high inflation rates, decreasing exchange rate of the local currency against the US dollar, low GDP, a sharp decrease in the demand and supply of loans, an increase in problem loans, and increased default risk (ESCWA, 2020). Amid these unstable economic conditions, private banks lowered their lending activities, accumulated non-earnings liquid assets, and hid their losses by reporting unrealized gains and losses in their financial statements (Al Mashhour, Asalie, Abd Aziz, & Noor, 2020). Even though, these banks are still operating in Syria.

Theoretical Framework

The user perspective adopted by accounting standard setters globally emphasizes the importance of providing decision-useful accounting information (Garrod, Giner, & Laran, 2000). To be useful, accounting information must be relevant, meaning it should reflect values that are pertinent to investors in making their decisions (Mulenga & Bhatia, 2018; Olugbenga & Oyerinde, 2014). Value relevance also refers to the ability of accounting information to capture or summarize information influencing market values (Beisland, 2009). Additionally, value relevance is understood as the extent to which accounting information reflects or correlates with market value, such as stock prices and returns (Oyerinde, 2009). This relationship's strength is often quantified through statistical associations between accounting metrics and market indicators (Francis & Schipper, 1999).

The study of the value relevance of accounting information has evolved significantly over time. Initial research adopted an information-based approach (Beaver, 1968; Ball & Brown, 1968), focusing on market reactions to accounting disclosures (Amir, Harris, & Venuti, 1993). These studies are based on the hypothesis that the market is informationally efficient, whereby new information is quickly incorporated into security prices, influencing investor decisions (Kothari, 2001). However, as research progressed, the focus shifted toward a measurement-based approach grounded in equity valuation theories proposed by Ohlson (1995). This transition marked a move from assessing market reactions to examining the intrinsic relationship between accounting metrics and market valuations.

Ohlson's (1995) framework has been particularly influential in shaping contemporary value relevance research. It provides a theoretical and empirical basis for analyzing the interplay between earnings, book value of equity, and security prices or yields. Consequently, association-based studies have focused on the correlation between accounting metrics and market share prices (price models) or market returns (return models) (Dahmash & Qabajeh, 2012; Easton & Harris, 1991). Importantly, association-based studies do not claim that accounting reports are the sole source of information for market participants, nor do they assert a direct causal relationship between accounting metrics and share prices. (Kothari, 2001).

Recent scholarship emphasizes the importance of expanding value relevance research to encompass other accounting metrics, such as cash flows and revenue recognition practices (Esfandani, Ahmadi, & Borghei, 2024). These dimensions offer additional

insights into a firm's financial health and its future viability, thereby enhancing investors' decision-making processes.

This study is an association-based analysis that examines the association between accounting metrics (such as book value of equity, earnings, and information from the cash flows statement) and share prices. It analyses the incremental and relative value relevance of cash flow information compared to earnings. The following diagram (Figure 1) explains the different concepts of the analysis based on the theoretical framework:

Figure 1. Analyzing the association between share prices and accounting metrics

This study specifically focuses on the value relevance of cash flow statement components within the banking sector. Cash flow statements are critical for assessing a firm's liquidity, solvency, and operational efficiency—factors that are particularly paramount in industries like banking, where cash flows are central to financial stability and performance. By examining the relationship between cash flow components and market valuations, the study aims to provide deeper insights into how these elements influence investor perceptions and decision-making processes in the banking sector.

Literature review

The value relevance of cash flow statements in the banking sector has been explored in various studies, revealing a spectrum of findings and critical discussions regarding their incremental informativeness. Barth et al. (1999) established a foundational analysis by examining a dataset of 15,405 firm-year observations across 14 different industries from 1987 to 1996. Their research revealed that cash flows provide incremental value relevance in all investigated industries, including financial institutions. Contrastingly, Bolibok

(2015) focused on the Polish banking sector, analyzing data from 18 listed commercial banks from 1997 to 2014. This study highlighted that net earnings and book value of equity were perceived as value relevant, while operating cash flows showed no statistically significant association with share prices. This raises questions about the usefulness of cash flow metrics in different market contexts and emphasizes the need to explore methodological limitations in prior research critically. Dimitropoulos, Asteriou, and Koumanakos (2010) contributed to the discussion by examining the comparative usefulness of cash flows and earnings within the Greek banking sector. Their findings indicated earnings were more effective in explaining stock returns, yet they acknowledged that both metrics retained importance for valuation. The inconsistent results across studies may be due to variations in research methods and the unique characteristics of banking environments. Further reinforcing the mixed findings, Burke and Wieland (2017) analyzed 4,897 bank-year observations from the U.S.A., revealing a significant positive relationship between operating cash flows and share prices. They noted that this relationship was influenced by capital adequacy, credit risk, and profitability. Their results prompt further inquiry into the contextual factors that might alter the value relevance of cash flows in different banking conditions.

Gao et al. (2019) expanded the analysis by examining a dataset comprising 594 publicly listed commercial banks and 5,217 industrial firms to evaluate whether cash flow statements offer incremental value relevance compared to data from balance sheets and income statements. Their analysis revealed a limited incremental usefulness of operating cash flows and indicated that the arbitrary division between operating and non-operating cash flows in banks' cash flow statements was not particularly informative.

Lastly, Ryan (2006) conducted an empirical analysis of various components of banks' cash flow statements, examining 330 observations from U.S. commercial banks and thrifts between 1991 and 2003. His findings indicated that activities classified as operating exhibited a mixed nature, resulting in a weaker positive correlation between cash flows from these activities and expected operating cash flows, as well as stock returns, when compared to accruals and more straightforward operating cash flow components. In contrast, hybrid activities demonstrated a stronger positive relationship with anticipated operating cash flows and stock returns than investing or financing cash flows. This raises the question of whether categorizing banks' cash flows into operating, investing, and financing activities remains appropriate, or if further distinctions are needed to reflect the unique nature of banks and their financial services.

Research on the market relevance of operating cash flows and other accounting figures has gained traction across diverse global regions, including the U.S., EU, Far Eastern countries, and the Arab world. A notable study by El-Diftar and Elkalla (2019) specifically analyzed the utility of key accounting metrics within the context of Arab nations, comparing six Gulf countries with three non-Gulf nations: Egypt, Jordan, and Tunisia. Utilizing data from 798 non-financial firms and covering the period from 2007 to 2016, their findings revealed that equity, earnings, and operating cash flows maintained their market relevance across the overall sample and in both sub-samples. However, notably, the coefficient for operating cash flows specific to the Gulf countries was statistically insignificant, suggesting a potential divergence in the value placed on cash flow metrics in these economies. Moreover, the study revealed a decline in the market

relevance of accounting metrics post-IFRS adoption in the MENA region. This finding challenges the assumed universality of IFRS benefits, highlighting the need for region-specific research into the institutional or market factors driving these outcomes.

Recent studies have further emphasized the dynamic nature of cash flow relevance, particularly during periods of economic uncertainty. For example, Abou-El-Sood (2023) found that the value relevance of cash flows significantly increased during the Covid-19 pandemic, suggesting that investors relied more heavily on cash flows for valuation purposes during times of crisis. However, the study also revealed that the distinction between operating and non-operating cash flows was not particularly informative. Similarly, Čupić, Todorović, and Benković (2023) demonstrated that earnings are more value-relevant than cash flows in non-financial firms, though regulatory improvements can enhance the value relevance of financial information. These findings underscore the importance of context in assessing the relevance of cash flow information.

In summary, while significant contributions have been made to understanding banks' cash flow statements, prior studies have revealed mixed results that emphasize the need for a more critical and comprehensive analysis.

Model Specifications and Data

This study employs a model founded on the work of (Ohlson, 1995), implemented by (Collins, Maydew, & Weiss, 1997) and used by (Burke & Wieland, 2017):

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \varepsilon \quad (1)$$

In this context, P denotes the closing share price adjusted for stock splits and dividends at the end of the third month after the conclusion of the financial year, while EPS refers to earnings per share, and $BVPS$ indicates the book value of equity per share at the beginning of the period.

By including earnings (as an aggregate figure), it is assumed implicitly that all earnings' components are identically associated with share prices (Beisland, 2009). To relax this assumption, the study follows (Burke & Wieland, 2017) and decomposes earnings into operating cash flows and total accruals:

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 CFOPS + \beta_3 ACCPS + \varepsilon \quad (2)$$

where $CFOPS$ defined as operating cash flows per share and $ACCPS$ is total accruals per share ($ACCPS = EPS - CFOPS$).

The study also evaluates the additional and comparative usefulness of operating cash flows. Based on the distinction made by (Biddle, Seow, & Siegel, 1995) and cited by (Beisland, 2009) and also following (Charitou, Clubb, & Andreou, 2000; Bepari, Rahman, & Taher Molik, 2013), the model outlined below is used to investigate the additional usefulness of operating cash flows:

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 CFOPS + \varepsilon \quad (3)$$

A significant coefficient of operating cash flows indicates additional value relevance of this accounting figure beyond earnings and book value of equity. In addition, to evaluate the relative value relevance, the study uses the following model:

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_2 BVPS + \beta_3 CFOPS + \varepsilon \quad (4)$$

Based on the argument used by Charitou, Clubb, & Andreou (2000), the explanatory power of model 4 will be compared with that of model 1 to determine whether operating cash flows are more value relevant compared to earnings.

The study also examines the significance of additional information included in the cash flow statement. To fulfill this purpose, the study follows (Tahat & Alhadab, 2017) approach by adding two models that include investing cash flows and financing cash flows, as follows:

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 CFIPS + \varepsilon \quad (5)$$

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 CFFPS + \varepsilon \quad (6)$$

where CFIPS and CFFPS are cash flows from investing and financing activities, respectively.

Data are collected manually from published financial reports of the eleven conventional private banks operating in Syria. Islamic banks were excluded due to their different business model. The study extends from 2010 to 2022, which gives a total of 143 firm-year observations. While the sample size of 143 firm-year observations provides meaningful insights into the value relevance of cash flow statements in the Syrian banking sector, it is relatively small compared to studies in more stable economies. This may limit the generalizability of the findings to broader contexts. However, the sample is representative of the Syrian banking sector, which consists of a limited number of private banks operating under unique economic and regulatory conditions. Future research could expand the sample size by including additional years or cross-country comparisons to enhance the robustness of the findings.

The data utilized for this study was manually extracted from the annual reports of Syrian private banks, publicly accessible in PDF format. This data was sourced from the websites of the Damascus Stock Exchange and the Syrian Commission of Financial Markets and Securities. By including all Syrian private banks listed on the Damascus Stock Exchange during the study period, we aimed to mitigate biases, such as survivorship bias, which could arise from focusing only on currently active institutions.

Additionally, we recognized the potential limitations of self-reported financial data and implemented rigorous precautions to ensure accuracy during the extraction process. While we acknowledge that reporting biases may still exist due to regulatory or economic conditions in Syria, we believe our systematic data collection and verification processes have minimized their impact on the study's findings.

Regarding the choice of pooled OLS regression, our study focuses on examining the average associations across the sample rather than capturing individual heterogeneity,

which is better suited for panel data methods such as fixed or random effects models. By incorporating control variables that account for bank-specific characteristics, such as size, leverage, and liquidity hoarding, we enhance the robustness of the model and mitigate potential biases. This approach aligns with our research objectives, prioritizing understanding the average relationships within the context of Syrian private banks. Additionally, the applicability of panel data analysis is constrained by several factors. First, the small sample size, resulting from the limited number of Syrian private banks, restricts the feasibility of employing panel data techniques. Second, the banks in our sample commenced operations between 2006 and 2010, limiting the time dimension for panel analysis.

While we acknowledge the advantages of panel data analysis in capturing individual heterogeneity and dynamic effects, we believe that pooled OLS regression is more appropriate for our study, given the nature of the data and research objectives. This method allows us to focus on the average associations while addressing potential biases through the inclusion of relevant control variables.

This study follows methodologies established in prior research (Akbar, Shah, & Stark, 2011; Tahat & Alhadab, 2017; Acaranupong, 2017; Berrios, 2013; Petria, Capraru, & Ihnatov, 2015; Ragab & El-Chaarani, 2018) by controlling for firm size (measured as the natural logarithm of total assets), leverage (total liabilities divided by total equity), and liquidity hoarding (net loans to customer deposits ratio). Firm size (ln total assets) is a standard control in financial research, as larger institutions often exhibit distinct performance patterns compared to smaller ones, ensuring that scale-related biases are minimized. The leverage ratio is included to capture financial stability and risk exposure, given that higher leverage can magnify the impact of economic factors on bank performance. Additionally, liquidity hoarding is specifically accounted for due to the unique context of Syrian banks, which, unlike many global counterparts, face limited liquidity risk. This metric is crucial for understanding the operational and financial behavior of banks in this setting. Although other variables could be relevant, these three controls were selected for their alignment with the Syrian banking environment and their established significance in bank performance literature.

We calculated Pearson pairwise correlations and variance inflation factors (VIF) to address potential multicollinearity. For heteroscedasticity, we implemented two corrective measures: (1) scaling all variables by the number of shares outstanding at year-end to mitigate size-related heteroscedasticity, and (2) conducting a Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test to assess error-term heteroscedasticity. The test (Table 2) yielded a statistically significant p-value ($p < 0.001$, $\chi^2(1) = 202.03$), leading us to reject the null hypothesis of constant variance. To correct for this, we applied White's (1980) heteroscedasticity-consistent covariance estimator in our regression models.

Table 2. Breusch-Pagan/Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity

Breusch-Pagan/ Cook-Weisberg test for heteroskedasticity Ho: Constant variance Variables: fitted values of P	
chi2(1)	202.03
Prob> chi2	0.000

Given concerns about endogeneity—particularly the lack of theoretical guidance on endogenous variables in the Ohlson model—we conducted robustness checks: (1) adding control variables to minimize omitted variable bias and (2) estimating a fixed effects (FE) model to address time-invariant unobserved confounders. The FE results indicated consistent coefficient magnitudes, signs, and significance levels compared to the baseline model, suggesting limited endogeneity from time-invariant factors. However, we did not employ lagged variables as instrumental variables since the model does not assume causality between share prices and accounting metrics. Remaining concerns include unobserved time-varying confounders, selection bias, and measurement error.

Finally, a Ramsey RESET test for omitted variables (Table 3) failed to reject the null hypothesis ($p = 0.1101$, $F(3, 133) = 2.05$), indicating no evidence of model misspecification. While these measures mitigate endogeneity concerns, we acknowledge that they do not fully resolve the issue, which remains a study limitation.

Table 3. Ramsey RESET test for omitted variable

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of P Ho: model has no omitted variables	
F (3, 133)	2.05
Prob> F	0.1101

Results

Descriptive statistics

Table 4 presents descriptive statistics for key financial metrics of Syrian banks during a period of significant economic instability and high inflation. The mean Earnings per Share (EPS) of 192.77 appears relatively low, which is likely attributable to inflationary pressures, currency depreciation, and constrained banking operations. Despite this, banks generated positive Operating Cash Flow per Share (CFOPS, mean = 258.10), indicating their ability to maintain liquidity from core activities. The negative Investing Cash Flow per Share (CFIPS, mean = -453.21) suggests reduced capital expenditures or asset disposals, a common survival strategy during financial distress. Meanwhile, near-neutral Financing Cash Flow per Share (CFFPS, mean = 9.93) reflects limited need to external funding due to economic conditions where banks hoard liquidity. The negative Accruals per Share (ACCPS) implies that earnings were more cash-based than accounting-based, a trend often observed in volatile economies.

Table 4. Descriptive statistic

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
BVPS	143	471.8582	529.7031	5.681518	5.681518
EPS	143	192.7745	332.2194	-104.4431	1397.416
CFOPS	143	258.1026	743.6495	-1793.36	4244.337
ACCPS	143	-65.32806	600.2142	-3120.037	2147.57
CFIPS	143	-453.208	5271.972	-63025.18	1194.364
CFFPS	143	9.928989	49.9872	-40.91427	332.9069

The correlation matrix reveals several key relationships among the variables. Most notably, operating cash flows (CFOPS) exhibit a strong negative correlation with accruals (ACCPS) at -0.899, which aligns with prior literature (e.g., Burke & Wieland, 2017; Dechow, 1994) and reflects the inherent inverse relationship between accrual accounting and cash flow timing. This high correlation is also evident from the variance inflation factor for operating cash flows and accruals (Table 6) which exceeds the threshold of 5. This suggests that as accruals increase, operating cash flows tend to decrease—a pattern consistent with the smoothing function of accruals in financial reporting (Dechow, 1994; Dechow, Kothari, & Watts, 1998; Bushman, Lerman, & Hang, 2016; Green, Louis, & Sani, 2022). Such a strong association could raise multicollinearity concerns. To address this concern, accruals (ACCPS) are excluded from the final regression analysis.

Additionally, share prices (P) show a strong positive correlation with book value per share (BVPS) (0.711), underscoring the relevance of liquidation value for investors, particularly in Syria's high-risk banking environment. Earnings per share (EPS) also correlates moderately with share prices (0.445) and BVPS (0.484), reinforcing the role of profitability and equity value in pricing. The weak or negligible correlations involving financing cash flows (CFFPS) and investing cash flows (CFIPS) suggest these variables have limited linear relationships with other metrics in this context. The VIF-values for the other variables are under the threshold of 5.

These findings support the theoretical expectation that accruals and cash flows capture distinct aspects of financial performance, with the former reflecting accounting adjustments and the latter representing actual liquidity movements. The results further emphasize the importance of book value in investor decision-making during periods of economic instability.

Table 5. Correlation matrix

Variable	P	BVPS	EPS	CFOPS	ACCPS	CFIPS	
P	1.0000						
BVPS	0.7114*	1.0000					
EPS	0.4454*	0.4844*	1.0000				
CFOPS	0.2077*	0.0928	0.6135*	1.0000			
ACCPS	-0.0109	0.1531	-0.2066*	0.8994*	1.0000		
CFIPS	-0.1190	-0.1650*	-0.0162	0.0065	-0.017	1.0000	
CFFPS	-0.0519	-0.1234	-0.1409	-0.0929	0.0371	0.0141	1.0000

* Indicates statistically significant at the 5% level

Table 6. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
ACCP	7.50	0.133314
CFOPS	7.43	0.134549
BVPS	1.50	0.665464
CFIPS	1.04	0.965410
EPS	1.03	0.974272
CFFPS	1.03	0.975239
Mean VIF	3.25	

Regression results

Table 7 presents the regression analysis for Model (1), where share price (P) is explained by the book value per share ($BVPS$) and earnings per share (EPS). The model is statistically significant ($p < 0.001$), with an R^2 of 51.93%, indicating that these two variables account for approximately 52% of the variation in share prices. Both $BVPS$ and EPS exhibit significant coefficients at the 5% level, confirming their relevance in explaining share price movements.

The standardized coefficients reveal that $BVPS$ ($\beta = 0.6605$) has nearly twice the influence of EPS ($\beta = 0.3718$), suggesting that investors in Syrian banks place greater emphasis on book value—a proxy for liquidation value—than on current earnings. This aligns with the heightened risk of bankruptcy and economic instability during the study period.

The dominance of $BVPS$ supports prior findings on the importance of equity value in distressed markets, while the secondary role of EPS underscores its persistent, albeit weaker, relevance. The model's robustness (F-statistic = 36.38, $p = 0.0000$) reinforces the validity of these relationships.

Model 3 demonstrates that when operating cash flows ($CFOPS$) are incorporated alongside book value ($BVPS$) and earnings (EPS), $CFOPS$ fails to show statistical significance ($p=0.224$) and even renders EPS insignificant ($p=0.664$), while $BVPS$ maintains strong significance ($p<0.001$). This suggests that in Syria's extreme economic conditions, investors primarily rely on book value as their key decision metric, essentially disregarding both earnings and cash flow information. The standardized coefficients confirm this hierarchy, with $BVPS$ ($\beta=0.6509$) dominating EPS ($\beta=0.3632$) and $CFOPS$ ($\beta=0.1163$). This pattern persists even when examining Model 4, where $CFOPS$ only gains marginal significance ($p=0.021$) when EPS is excluded, though its economic impact remains minimal ($\beta=0.1377$). These findings contradict conventional financial theory and several empirical studies (e.g., Cheng et al., 1996; Charitou et al., 2000) that advocate for cash flows' superiority in uncertain environments, but align with Bepari et al.'s (2013) crisis-period findings. The results likely reflect Syria's unique circumstances: banks' liquidity hoarding behavior due to extreme credit risk, investors' survivalist focus on liquidation value, and potential distortions in both earnings and cash flow metrics. The minimal improvement in explanatory power (R^2 increasing from 51.93% to just 52.72%

when adding CFOPS) further confirms that cash flows provide negligible incremental information. This study thus highlights how severe economic instability can fundamentally alter the value relevance of financial metrics, with traditional assumptions about cash flow usefulness potentially reversing in crisis contexts. The findings emphasize the need for context-specific valuation models in distressed economies, where conventional financial statement analysis may require significant adaptation. This behavior aligns with the findings of Bepari, Rahman, and Mollik (2013), who observed a decline in the relevance of operating cash flows during the 2008 financial crisis. However, our results contrast with those of Tahat and Alhadab (2017), who found that the 2008 crisis did not diminish the value relevance of operating cash flows.

Table 7. Regression results of the main model and with operating cash flows

Panel A		
Model (1) $P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \varepsilon$		
Variable	Coef. (p-value)	
BVPS	.8757035*** (0.000)	
EPS	.2838065** (0.035)	
C	197.162*** (0.000)	
R-squared = 0.5193	F (2, 140) = 36.38	Prob> F = 0.0000
Panel B		
Model (3) $P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 CFOPS + \varepsilon$		
Variable	Coef. (p-value)	
BVPS	.9181349*** (0.000)	
EPS	.095607 (0.664)	
CFOPS	.1131815 (0.224)	
C	184.208*** (0.000)	
R-squared = 0.5272	F(3, 139) = 23.40	Prob > F = 0.0000
Panel c		
Model (4) $P = \beta_0 + \beta_2 BVPS + \beta_3 CFOPS + \varepsilon$		
Variable	Coef. (p-value)	
BVPS	.9439915*** (0.000)	
CFOPS	.1376747** (0.021)	
C	184.1162*** (0.000)	
R-squared = 0.5263	F (2, 140) = 27.84	Prob> F = 0.0000

***, **, and * refer to significance at the levels 1%, 5%, and 10%, respectively

The discrepancies regarding the value relevance of operating cash flows underscore the importance of context-specific factors, such as the severity of economic instability and investor behavior, in shaping the value relevance of financial metrics.

To verify whether negative cash flows from operation caused the absence of its incremental usefulness, the study follows Papadatos & Makri (2013) and adds a dummy variable that is set to 1 when operating cash flows are positive, and 0 when they are not.

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_2 BVPS + \beta_3 CFOPS + \beta_4 D + \beta_5 D \times CFOPS + \varepsilon \quad (7)$$

Where D is the dummy variable and D X CFOPS represents its interaction with cash flows from operation.

An F-test is conducted to verify whether adding these two variables significantly improves the model. The F test has shown that the coefficients of the dummy variable and its interaction did not differ significantly from zero.

Collins, Maydew, & Weiss (1997) mentioned that changes in the usefulness of equity and net income are associated with firm size. The study follows (Dimitropoulos, Asteriou, & Koumanakos, 2010) and (Bepari, Rahman, & Mollik, 2013) by adding a dummy variable that is set to 1 when the size is greater than the median value, and 0 when it is not. The untabulated outcome shows that the coefficient for the interaction between this dummy variable and cash flows from operating activities was not significant

The results of models (5) and (6), as presented in Table 8, indicate that the coefficients for CFIPS (cash flows from investing activities) and CFFPS (cash flows from financing activities) are statistically insignificant. This suggests that the cash flow statement did not provide useful information for Syrian investors during the studied period. A plausible explanation for this finding is the prolonged unrest in Syria, which severely impacted the economy and heightened bankruptcy risks. In such uncertain conditions, firms significantly reduced their investing and financing activities, and investors may have shifted their focus toward the liquidation value of banks rather than their operational cash flows. The average net investing cash flows were negative (-453.208), reflecting banks' inability to expand their operations. Instead, they focused on maintaining existing operations amid challenging conditions. Similarly, the average net financing cash flows were relatively low (9.93), indicating that Syrian banks were hoarding liquidity and did not seek additional financing resources. These factors collectively explain why investing and financing cash flows did not demonstrate significant value relevance in the study.

The regression models were rerun as robustness checks after including the selected control variables (size, capital adequacy ratio, and liquidity hoarding). The untabulated results with these controls were qualitatively similar to those without them, suggesting that the findings are not significantly influenced by omitted variable bias or heterogeneity related to these financial characteristics. This consistency reinforces the reliability of the baseline results.

Table 8. Regression results with investing and financing cash flows

Panel A		
Model (5) $P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 CFIPS + \epsilon$		
2r Variable	Coef. (p-value)	
BVPS	.8728336*** (0.000)	
EPS	.285662** (0.037)	
CFIPS	-.001404 (0.634)	
C	197.5222*** (0.000)	
R-squared = 0.5194	F(3, 139) = 473.92	Prob>F = 0.0000
Panel B		
Model (6) $P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 BVPS + \beta_2 EPS + \beta_3 CFFPS + \epsilon$		
Variable	Coef. (p-value)	
BVPS	.880348*** (0.000)	
EPS	.2947136** (0.031)	
CFFPS	.6836272 (0.336)	
C	186.0801 (0.000)	
R-squared = 0.5215	F(3, 139) = 28.19	Prob > F = 0.0000

Discussion of the results

The study found no significant incremental or relative value relevance for cash flows from operating activities when compared to net income. This aligns with the findings of Bolibok (2015) and Gao, Li, & O'Hanlon (2019), who also reported a weak or insignificant relationship between operating cash flows and stock prices. Conversely, this conclusion contrasts with the observations of Burke & Wieland (2017) and Barth, Beaver, Hand, & Landesman (1999), who noted a positive and significant link between operating cash flows and stock prices, highlighting the additional utility of these cash flows. These findings contribute to Ohlson's model by demonstrating that the value relevance of accounting information is context-dependent. In stable environments, operating cash flows may serve as a reliable indicator of firm performance. However, in crisis-like environments, such as the one studied here, the relevance of operating cash flows diminishes, consistent with Ohlson's emphasis on earnings and book value as key determinants of equity value over cash flow measures. Bepari, Rahman, & Mollik (2013) also documented a decrease in the relevance of operating cash flows for investors in the Australian market amid the 2008 financial crisis. This challenges the assumption of general applicability in value relevance models and underscores the need to incorporate contextual factors, such as economic instability, into theoretical frameworks.

These findings have implications beyond Syria. In other emerging markets or crisis-affected economies, the value relevance of cash flow statements may similarly be influenced by macroeconomic instability and investor behavior. For example, in economies experiencing hyperinflation or political unrest, investors may place greater emphasis on liquidity and tangible assets rather than traditional cash flow metrics.

A detailed examination of the components of operating cash flows in the 2022 annual financial reports of Syrian banks reveals that variations in these cash flows were predominantly driven by changes in customer deposits and balances with other banks, rather than shifts in loan activity. In 2022, net loans constituted only 16.42% of total assets, while liquid non-interest-bearing assets represented approximately 73% of total assets. Consequently, the observed positive operating cash flows are likely derived from fund flows not directed toward interest-generating assets. This situation may cause Syrian investors to disregard operating cash flows, perceiving them as offering limited relevant information. The insignificant coefficients of cash flows from investing activities and cash flows from financing activities suggest that the cash flow statement did not provide useful information for Syrian investors during the studied period. A plausible explanation for this finding is the prolonged unrest in Syria, which severely impacted the economy and heightened bankruptcy risks. In such uncertain conditions, firms significantly reduced their investing and financing activities, and investors may have shifted their focus toward the liquidation value of banks rather than their cash flows. The average net investing cash flows were negative (-453.208), reflecting banks' inability to expand their operations. Instead, they focused on maintaining existing operations amid challenging conditions. Similarly, the average net financing cash flows were relatively low (9.93), indicating that Syrian banks were hoarding liquidity and did not seek additional financing resources. These factors collectively explain why investing and financing cash flows did not demonstrate significant value relevance in the study.

This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, the focus on Syrian banks limits the generalizability of the findings to other contexts. Second, the small sample size and simplified measurement of cash flow components may affect the robustness of the results. Third, the reliance on self-reported financial data introduces potential biases. Future research could address these limitations by expanding the sample to include banks from other emerging markets, using more granular measures of cash flow components, and incorporating alternative data sources. Additionally, future studies could explore the value relevance of cash flow statements in other emerging markets or during different phases of economic crises. For example, researchers could investigate how the value relevance of cash flows changes during periods of economic recovery versus periods of decline. Furthermore, future research could examine the role of alternative financial metrics, such as liquidity ratios or non-financial indicators, in crisis environments.

Conclusion

This study arises from the ongoing discourse surrounding the utility of cash flow statements in the banking sector, which operates under distinct dynamics compared to other firms. Traditional classifications of cash flows into operating, financing, and investing categories may not effectively capture the cash flow behavior unique to banks.

By investigating the link between cash flows and stock prices, this research seeks to assess whether the current format of cash flow statements provides valuable insights for investors. The findings reveal that operating cash flows do not contribute additional value beyond what is already provided by earnings. Moreover, the explanatory power of a model that integrates operating cash flows is not meaningfully different from that of a model based solely on earnings. Additionally, both investing and financing cash flows lack the ability to yield significant information for investors. In light of the challenging economic landscape in Syria, cash flow statements may not hold substantial relevance for local investors.

These findings have important implications for policymakers in emerging markets. In crisis-affected economies, regulators could consider requiring additional disclosures related to liquidity and asset quality, which may be more relevant in unstable environments. Additionally, policymakers could promote the use of alternative performance metrics that better capture the financial health of firms in crisis settings. This study also contributes to the literature on value relevance by highlighting the role of contextual factors, such as economic instability, in shaping the usefulness of financial information. It challenges the assumption of universal applicability in value relevance models and calls for a more nuanced understanding of how investor behavior and macroeconomic conditions influence the relevance of financial metrics.

Future research could build on these findings by exploring the value relevance of cash flow statements in other emerging markets or during different phases of economic crises. Additionally, researchers could investigate the role of alternative financial metrics, such as liquidity ratios or non-financial indicators, in crisis environments. By addressing these questions, future studies could provide valuable insights for both academics and practitioners. Ultimately, this research underscores the importance of adapting financial reporting practices to reflect the unique challenges of crisis-affected economies, ensuring that financial information remains relevant and useful for investors.

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